

Policy Brief

Innovative ways to finance the resilience of the cultural landscape

Why this policy brief?

Cultural landscapes (CLs) are landscapes whose character is the result of the historic action and interaction of natural and human factors with significant cultural significance for the communities that live in them and intrinsic resilience. Climate resilience of CLs entails significant costs and thus requires structural investments and innovative financial and business strategies. Productive CLs are **dynamic socio-ecological systems**, and thus, their resilience demands a holistic approach that addresses not only the physical dimension but also ensures the continuity of underlying productive activities that shaped these landscapes. This policy brief was developed within the **RescueME project** focused on a landscape approach to resilience, aiming to protect cultural heritage and landscapes.

What does it cover?

Despite the growing interest, the existing body of knowledge on resilience financing for CLs and heritage is somehow fragmented, and primarily focuses on the conservation or reuse of the built heritage. Based on a systematic review of existing literature, insights from prior projects, and contributions from five pilot Resilience Landscapes (**R-Labscapes**), this policy brief covers the **benefits** and **enabling factors** of innovative economic, financing, and business (EFB) strategies that can leverage regenerative capital investments for landscape resilience. These EFB strategies are compiled in the RescueMe **meta-repository**, with detailed information available in the accompanying **Factsheets**.

Who should read this?

This policy brief targets a broad audience, including policymakers, cultural and

environmental NGOs, researchers, and practitioners. The **policymakers** at national, regional, and local levels can use this brief to facilitate funding and business opportunities for CLs. The **NGOs, researchers, and practitioners** can use the brief to advocate for increased support and resources to streamline funding into CLs.

Key messages

Investing in CLs offers socio-economic and environmental benefits, including enhanced social cohesion, urban regeneration, and enhanced biodiversity.

Key enablers for successful implementation of EFB strategies in CLs include stakeholder engagement, strategic planning, and a commitment to sustainability, among others.

Aligning sectoral policies and mapping funds can boost investments into CLs.

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What are the benefits of financing CLs resilience?

Numerous “side” benefits of investing in the resilience of CLs, extending beyond the protection of their tangible dimension:

Social cohesion

refers to the sense of belonging of a community to its CL and is achieved when needs and objectives of each individual and group is recognised. In the case of CLs, strategies based on income diversification, social entrepreneurship, hybrid and impact funding, have contributed to the social cohesion promotion of gender-inclusive economic development and creating prosperity for its marginalised community members, as observed in the case of B-Corp Conservatorio.

B-Corp Conservatorio (PA)

Hazard: fast urban expansion, abandonment and dilapidation of historic architecture

Solution: Conservatorio is a for-profit real estate development company with B-Corp (Benefit Corporation) certification. Founded in 2005, it specialises in investing in historic urban areas, acquiring and restoring historical buildings for reuse, and engaging in brownfield development through new construction.

Impact: Conservatorio prioritises community social objectives in its projects and offers both debt and equity investment opportunities, with the latter providing market-rate returns.

Source: Uricheck et al. (2021)

Urban regeneration

Is embodied in resolving urban challenges and achieving lasting improvement in the socio-economic, physical and environmental condition of an urban landscape. Several financing strategies have demonstrated the contribution to urban regeneration through the renovation of public spaces and the stimulation of growth in local property values.

Environmental benefits

can take on multiple forms, including improved ecosystem services, enhanced biodiversity, reduction of soil degradation and chemical pollution, specifically when applied to agricultural landscapes subjected to the intensification of agricultural production.

Payment for environmental services

(PES) schemes in the Coffee CL (CO)

Hazard: environmental degradation, soil erosion, intensification of agricultural production

Solution: PES is a market-based approach to finance environmental conservation activities. In the case of Coffee CL, PES was led by International NGOs and used to secure environmental protection and economic stability of the coffee farms by incentivising producers to produce sustainably. Financial rewards were provided for adopting sustainable farming practices that protect the region's biodiversity and watershed.

Impact: The solution contributed to the use of sustainable agricultural practices and enhanced environmental sustainability, along with an increase in coffee producers' technical efficiency, encompassing socio-economic factors as well.

Source: Rodríguez et al (2022)

Enhancement of cultural heritage values

is a “non material benefit”, that refers to the increase of heritage value and appreciation of CLs among local and wider communities (e.g., tourists). Investing into CLs results in

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restoring heritage values of urban and industrial brownfields.

Enhanced visibility of local production

is achieved when a set of symbols, cultures, and identities transformed into distinctive brands, whether in a planned or organic manner. This was observed in the case of business strategies based on territorial branding.

Eco-labelling for the Traditional Vineyards of Donana (SP)

Hazard: soil erosion, agricultural abandonment

Solution: Traditional vineyards around Donana National Park in southwestern Spain are facing soil erosion and a decline in ecosystem services. To tackle this, eco-labelling, specifically the Donana 21 scheme, is proposed as a financial incentive for farmers to manage these vineyards and reduce erosion, which is vital for preserving the Donana wetlands. Donana 21 certifies Andalusian products that meet certain quality and environmental standards, including local wines. Eco-labelling for wine-related products aims to raise consumer awareness about the environmental and socio-economic importance of traditional vineyards and encourage responsible farming through

purchasing decisions. Price premiums for certified products would offer farmers additional income to maintain these traditional vineyards.

Impact: The business model contributed to the increase in the added value of the sector within the expanding market of organic and ecological products, highlighting the multifunctional role and significance of traditional vineyards and their services. This enhanced visibility extends beyond local residents to society as a whole.

Source: Gaitán-Cremasch et al (2017)

Improved livelihoods of local communities

Promoting and supporting income diversification, such as eco-tourism and agricultural processing, can create additional revenue streams, especially for cultural landscapes managed by vulnerable groups. As observed in the business strategies based on income diversification, better livelihoods for local communities can be achieved not only through increased financial benefits for farmers but also through improved access to affordable land that can enhance the overall well-being of the local farming community.

Example of Collaborative Business Strategy from R-Labscapes L'Horta de

València - Vorasenda (SP)

Hazard: heat waves, droughts, agricultural abandonment and urban and infrastructure expansion

Solution: Vorasenda is an agroecological initiative in Valencia's Horta that cultivates vegetables and fruits using sustainable practices. It follows the Community Supported Agriculture model. Vorasenda also operates "L'Alter de Vorasenda," a social space for selling their production and hosting cultural, educational, and artistic events. Vorasenda supplies 150 families, shops, cooperatives, community kitchens, catering services, and restaurants. Clients provide monthly contributions, ensuring a minimum income for the project, which they redeem through purchases over the month.

Impact: This business strategy ensures the economic profitability of local production and involves the local community, thereby protecting and enhancing the associated agricultural landscape.

Source: RescueMe meta-repository.

Increased awareness on risks

is associated with the introduction of crowdfunding and community financing. These financing instruments, often accompanied with communication campaigns can provide additional information on the risks to local heritage and landscapes. Consequently,

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awareness-raising and communication can attract additional funding for landscape resilience.

Climate change mitigation

is generally understood as “the lessening” of the potential adverse impacts of physical hazards through actions that reduce hazard, exposure, and vulnerability. Multiple forms of climate change mitigation were observed, including the reduction of GHG emissions from organic waste and fossil fuel associated with climate-smart business strategies.

Climate bond financing adaptation actions in Paris (FR)

Hazard: Heat waves

Solution: Bonds are fixed income instruments involving loans made by an investor to a borrower to finance projects. In the case of climate/green finance is raised for climate change mitigation or adaptation-related projects or programmes. In 2015, as part of the commitment undertaken within the Paris Climate and Energy Action Plan, the City of Paris issued the Climate Bond. The objective of this solution was to reduce the urban heat island effect and increase thermal comfort within the city. Credit Agricole CIB, HSBC and Société Générale CIB acted as joint lead managers of such operations. These banks have been

selected through competitive tendering to guide the City in the process. In this way, the City could rely on their expertise and meet the investor’s expectations. It was able to attract a large number of investors, more than expected.

Impact: With this mechanism, new trees were planted, and new parks were created, pursuing the goals of the Paris Adaptation Strategy.

Source: Climate-ADAPT

How to enable the EFB strategies?

Engage and collaborate with stakeholders

Engagement of stakeholders and communities is crucial to ensure alignment with local needs and priorities and build trust. There are multiple tools for effective stakeholder engagement, including open dialogues, innovation laboratories, social networking activities, site visits at the location, followed by a series of seminars and sub-group discussions to foster efficiency of such partnerships.

Plan strategically and ensure long-term commitment

Effective implementation of EFB strategies requires long-term commitment from all parties, particularly in hybrid funding involving multiple stakeholders. Establishing a strategic planning instrument, based on shared visions, fosters this commitment. Additionally, given the multifunctionality of CLs, their resilience requires navigating legal and institutional pluralism, aligning sectoral policy objectives, and mapping allocated funds to manage overlaps and conflicts effectively.

Provide institutional and regulatory support

Governmental support and structured regulatory framework is crucial in unlocking specific funding opportunities, especially in EFB strategies based on long-term partnerships, such as public-private partnerships and collaborative business strategies. Governmental support is particularly important for hybrid funding strategies, which involve EU funds and intergovernmental loans, as the government must approve and guarantee these funds. Additionally, government intervention in crowdfunding campaigns helps reduce uncertainty regarding fund usage.

Build capacity and expertise

Expertise and capacity building is important in promoting a broader application and acceptance within the community. This can be fostered through the introduction of ad-hoc

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extension services and ad hoc learning platforms.

Example of tools for building capacity and expertise

In the case of the Carbon certification scheme introduced in rural landscapes in Kenya, extension services played a crucial role in the widespread adoption of sustainable landscape management practices by farmers, ensuring continuity in farming practices post-certification approval.

Capacity building activities can be also implemented through ad hoc learning platform, as in the case of Biogas Initiative for agriculture in Indonesia, where the Climate Field Schools provided an ideal platform for promoting digesters, allowing farmers to grasp the intricacies of the technology over time and fostering broader understanding and acceptance within the community.

Source: RescueMe meta-repository

Raise awareness and communicate effectively

Stakeholders' awareness is crucial to ensure effective collaborations and a shared long-term vision. This is particularly important in implementing strategies based on crowdfunding and PPPs, where the stakeholders' awareness of long-term goals

and effective cooperation between concessionaires, consortiums, and public/private stakeholders are crucial, as evidenced by numerous conservation and environmental projects.

Commit to sustainability

Commitment to sustainability is essential for accessing innovative funding solutions. Emerging EFB strategies largely depend on environmental and socio-economic sustainability, especially those involving impact funding aimed at positive environmental and socio-cultural outcomes. Financial tools like climate and green bonds are seldom used for CLs, except in urban and protected areas. There is growing evidence of the adoption of climate-smart business strategies in the agricultural sector. Commitment to sustainable agriculture is seen as crucial for the adoption of carbon farming. This strategy mitigates climate change while providing an alternative means of supporting the livelihoods of key landscape custodians.

Where can I get more information?

1. Borin, E., Fantini, G. (2023). Participatory Governance as a Success Factor in Equity Crowdfunding Campaigns for Cultural Heritage. *Journal of Risk and Financial*

Management, 16(3), 172.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm16030172>

2. Gaitán-Cremaschi, D., Palomo, I., Baraibar Molina, S., De Groot, R., Gómez-Baggethun, E. (2017). Applicability of economic instruments for protecting ecosystem services from cultural agrarian landscapes in Doñana, *Land Use Policy*, 61, 185–195.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.11.011>
3. Pickerill, T. (2021). Investment Leverage for Adaptive Reuse of Cultural Heritage. *Sustainability*, 13(9),
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su13095052>
4. Uricheck et al. (2021). Case Studies in Heritage Regeneration, *Issuu.com*. 2021. Available online:
https://issuu.com/home/published/case_studies_in_heritage_regeneration

Databases:

5. CLIC “Circular models Leveraging Investments in Cultural heritage adaptive reuse”. Available at the [link](#)
6. ForHeritage project. Interreg Central Europe Programme. Available at the [link](#)
7. PANORAMA – Solutions for a Healthy Planet. Available at the [link](#)
8. RescueMe meta-repository. Soon available at the project’s [website](#)
9. European Climate Adaptation Platform Climate-ADAPT. Available at the [link](#)

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Five pilot **R-Labscapes** of the RescueMe project: Psiloritis in Crete (Greece), Neuwerk in Hamburg (Germany), Portovenere, Cinque Terre & the islands (Italy), L'Horta in Valencia (Spain) and the city of Zadar (Croatia).

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To find out more about RescueMe project and to access our resources, events and case studies, visit : <https://resilientculturallandscapes.eu/>

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